

ECONOMY IS AN EFFECT – ENTREPRENEURSHIP IS THE CAUSE

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ABSTRACT

Aim of the study: The aim of the study is to review entrepreneurial policy and its impact on the Indian economy.

Methodology: The prominence of research is assessed by the studying the recent government policy and analyzing content available on government and publication houses.

Finding: The flagship of entrepreneurship in India will not only boost the economy but also nullify the impact of the reservation systems. It will also generate job opportunity for unemployed youth and balanced regional development. And development does not occur spontaneously, a catalyst or agent is needed and this requires an entrepreneurial ability.

Managerial implications and scope for future work / limitations: The paper covers a considerable period of time (2014-2019). This study is a qualitative one, quantitative analysis can be done with the fact and figure to justify the authors claim.

Keywords: Economic development, innovation, entrepreneurship

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Economic development of a country is measured through its increase in real per capita income and the rate at which formation of capital occurs. There are several determinants which increases per capita income but entrepreneurship is one among them.

Initially it was believed that economic development is an automatic and self-regulated process and there is no room for entrepreneurship. Two classical economist Adam Smith & David Ricardo justified this by advocating on the concept of capital formation. The former explained it as more is the saving more is the investment whereas the later focused on mass production to earn more profit; more profit will leads to more saving which ultimately goes to capital formation. As a consequence of this development will occur spontaneously.

The modern theory describe on the concept of rate at which formation of capital occurs. No doubt good economic condition will lead to development. But that is not sufficient. As a nation if you want to cope with the other developed nation you need to accelerate your economic development. For this entrepreneurial ability plays a vital role and the act as a catalyst. It is the entrepreneur who fully explore the potentiality of the country's resources to produce goods by brings and combining them together. The countries like America, Russia & Japan believed this concept and implemented it at ground level, as a result of which they are finding themselves at the top of economically developed country list. However the role of entrepreneurship varies from economy to economy depending upon its material resources, industrial climate and the responsiveness of the political system to the entrepreneurial function.

2.1. MATERIAL RESOURCES

2.1.1 Human Resources

As far as resources are concern human resource plays a significant role in economic development. Increased working population in India is an added advantage over the leading economics developed countries. The age 29 is the average age per person in India compared to age 37 for China & age 48 for Japan. That means the major chunk of total population of India, i.e. about 64% will under the working age group. The GDP growth rate will also be get influence by this demographic potentiality. In this process India will experience a dynamic transformation. It is not only about the quantity of workforce but also the quality of workforce is very much essential to meet international demand. Under the Kaushal Vikash Yojana India is likely to produce 500 million skilled workforce by 2020.

2.1.2 Infrastructure

Infrastructure sector plays a vital role to drive Indian economy. It also highly responsible for boosting India's overall development. The power, dams, roads, bridges and urban infrastructure are coming under this sector.

With the spanning a total of 5.5 million kilometer, India positioned 2nd in road network in the world. In World Bank's Logistics Performance Index (LPI) 2018 India ranked 44th out of 167 countries.

It has been observed that there is a sharp rise in all parameter of infrastructure sector in India in last four years.

Determinants	For Year 2014	For Year 2018
Total national highways length	92,851 Kms	122,434 Kms

Ease of doing business - "Getting Electricity" ranking	137	24
Energy deficit	4.2%	0.7%
Number of airports	70	101

2.1.3 Incubation program

Startups with the support of Incubators bring their innovative ideas & business concept to reality. As incubators provides workspace, high-speed Internet connection, legal and intellectual property services and access to high-profile investors. With the help of incubators the entrepreneurs will get a community gathering. Where he will get a chance to interact with investors, technology innovators and famous businesspersons. He will also get a forum for open house session and brainstorm with other like-minded people.

In some cases the incubators send a shortlisted promising young entrepreneurs to abroad on an all-expense paid trip, to expose them startup environment outside India. They may get chance to interact with some of the famous tech gurus and entrepreneurs in the world.

2.1.4 Financial Resources

With a combined push by both government and private sector, India is undoubtedly one of the world's most vibrant capital markets.

The shareholders' rights can be protected by the Udyami Mitra which has been launched by SIDBI.

The Seed support system (SSS) provides financial assistance to startups with new and meritorious ideas, innovations and technologies.

Funds of funds: Providing funding support through a fund of funds with a corpus of Rs 10,000 Crore

2.2 INDUSTRIAL CLIMATE

Post-independence India has been released industrial policy around six times. Out of these six resolution IPR (Industrial policy resolution) 1948, 1956 & 1991 are more important, whereas IPR 1977, 1980 & 1990 are just the extension of IPR 1956.

Before 1991 economic reform India has socialistic pattern of economy, Indian government had put much restriction on foreign investment and foreign company so that many foreign company left India, company like IBM & Coca-Cola are among them.

Current Industrial Policy of Government of India is the Industrial Policy of 1991 which was a watershed moment in the Indian Economy. It fulfilled log-left demands of the industry such as removal of compulsory licensing, MRTP limit and other numerous bureaucratic bottlenecks. The

companies could establish new undertakings and implement expansion plans. These reforms were introductory in nature and the series of reforms continued and are continuing even today.

2.2.1 Licensing System

Under 1991 policy, only eighteen industries need to take license from the government but this list was further reduced to 5 in year 1999. This number was further brought down and current position is that only Atomic Energy and Railways are Government monopoly industries in the country. There have been proposals for allowing private control in atomic energy sector also.

2.2.2 Foreign Investment & Capital

To promote foreign investment in India, up to 51% FDI was allowed in 47 high priority industries. But it exceptional for the export trading houses. Up to 74% FDI was allowed for export. Now in most number of sectors government allows 100% FDI.

For negotiation and approval of FDI in selected areas a special empowered board is established called as Foreign Investment Promotion Board (FIPB).

2.2.3 Foreign Technology Agreements

For the technological enhancement in Indian Industries automatic permission was given for foreign technology agreements in high priority industries and norms were made easy in hiring of foreign technicians.

2.2.4 Amendment in Monopolistic and Restrictive Trade Practices (MRTP) Act

Some amendment were made in MRTP act like removal of threshold limits of assets, elimination of prior approval of central government before establishing of new undertakings, expansion of undertakings, merger, takeover etc.

2.2.5 Re-defining MSME

To stimulate growth in MSME the definition of MSME was made based on annual revenue instead of investment on plant and machinery. i.e.

Businesses with revenue of

- ✓ as much as Rs 5 crore Micro
- ✓ Rs 5 crore and Rs 75 crore Small
- ✓ Rs 75 crore and Rs 250 crore Medium

There is no distinction between manufacturing and service unit

2.2.6 Faster Exit for Startups

It was made easy for startups to wind-up operations on a fast track basis i.e. within 90 days and reallocate capital and resources to more productive.

2.2.7 Legal support and fast-tracking patent examination at lower costs

Legally protect innovation by fast track examination of patent application and increase the valuation of the innovation. Central government shall bear the entire fees of the facilitators and there is a rebate of 80% in filing of patents vis a vis other companies.

2.3 RESPONSIVENESS OF THE POLITICAL SYSTEM

According to Ease of Doing Business 2019 survey made by World Bank, India grabbed 77 rank among 190 countries. India is the only nation to have made it to the list of top 10 improvers for the second consecutive year. Last year, India saw a record jump of 30 places to reach the 100th position in the rankings.

A significant improvement has been seen in India's ranking. It was 142 in year 2014 to 77 in year 2018. There is an improvement of 65 places in ranking. Whereas under an "economist" PM, Dr. Manmohan Singh, India glided down 10 points in its ranking for "Ease of Doing Business" during the period 2011 to 2014 and ranked 142.

The remarkable upward move in India's "Ease of Doing Business Ranking," in last four years displays the successful implementation of economic reforms by the union government.

2.3.1 Determinants for ease of doing business

The determinates like Dealing with construction permits, Starting a business, Enforcing contracts, Trading across borders, Getting credit & Getting electricity connection, Registering property, Paying taxes, Resolving insolvency & Protecting minority investors measures the ease of doing business.

2.3.2 MSME

MSME plays a vital role in economic development and employment generation. In country like US, 60 to 70 % of jobs were generated through MSMEs. Therefore to enrich Indian economy the present Government led by Mr. Narendra Modi had taken some bold and historical steps to boost MSME in the country. In this decision he mainly focused on five key aspects, which includes

- ✓ Access to credit
- ✓ Access to market
- ✓ Technology up gradation
- ✓ Ease of doing business, and
- ✓ Sense of security for employees.

Access to Credit: Credit up to Rs. 1.crore can be accessible through GST Portal in just 59 minutes and MSME registered with GST will get rebate of 2% on an incremental loan.

For the exporters seeking loans on pre-shipment and post shipment, the rebate has been increased from 3% to 5%.

Access to Markets: It is made mandatory for all public sector companies to procure 25% of their total purchase from MSMEs. In this 25% procurement, 3% is reserved for the women entrepreneur. It was asked to all public sector undertakings to register under GeM (Government e-marketplace)

Technology Up gradation: Tool rooms plays a vital role for technological up gradation as it designs the product. Keeping this in view hub & spokes concept is introduced in which hundred spokes in the form of tool rooms will be controlled by 20 hubs across the country.

Ease of Doing Business: The government will form MSME pharma clusters. 70% cost of establishing these clusters will be borne by the government.

MSMEs will have to file just one annual return on eight labour laws and 10 central rules.

Inspections of factories in the MSME sector will be sanctioned only through a computerized random allotment.

An ordinance has been disseminated to simplify the levy of penalties for minor offences under the Companies Act.

Sense of security for employees:

Keeping the security of employees in tact it was ensure that every employee have Jan Dhan Accounts, Provident fund & insurance.

3.0 CONCLUSION

It is assumed that the entrepreneur contributes more in economy with relatively more favorable conditions then in the economy with relatively less favorable conditions. Hence what type of entrepreneur shall emerge in a country depends a lot on a type of facility that is political and economic setup available in that particular country.

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